

Reproduce experimental results from a paper

Experiment Design for Data Science 2020W (188.992) - Exercise 2
Group 7

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ABSTRACT

In this document, the process of attempting to reproduce the setup, experiments, and results as explained in a certain scientific paper is documented. The selected paper [3] questions the bias of recommender systems towards rewarding algorithms that recommend popular items with the question: "Should I Follow the Crowd? A Probabilistic Analysis of the Effectiveness of Popularity in Recommender Systems". It deals with the task of exploring the question whether popularity could be a useful and reliable signal in recommendation or should be avoided due to biases. The authors address this question at a formal level. They illustrate and confirm their theoretical findings with empirical results. In [3] they identified and modeled conditions to determine answers, in terms of dependencies between key random variables. They built a crowdsourced dataset, with which they exemplify contradictions between the accuracy of biased and unbiased observations.

Our upcoming task is to confirm the numbers, findings and results in [3] as exact as possible, or alternatively, uncover inconsistencies and therefore challenge the conclusions. Three different figures (3, 5 and 6) illustrate the experiments and in the following report we attempt to recreate the experiments as exact as possible in order to achieve the same results. In the first chapter we are setting up the experiment setup, whereas in the second chapter we will focus on reproduction of the results from the paper. Each following subsection in second chapter is dedicated to the figures 3, 5 and 6 and their respective experiments. If there were missing information in the experiments or noticeable deviations to our results in the paper, we explain them in detail in the respective subsections. After the comparisons of the results of the figures, we also focus on performing a detailed examination of the experimental setup to examine whether the values and conclusions reported in the paper also hold with different seeds in order to determine if the experiments were run multiple times and/or significance tests were performed.

KEYWORDS

evaluation, bias, non-random missing data, popularity, recommender systems, average rating, collaborative filtering, reproducibility, precision, nDCG, observed, true, relevance

1 EXPERIMENT SETUP

Setting up the experiment setup was, instead of the dozens other papers we analyzed, possible and straightforward. The software and the datasets can be downloaded on [2].

System Requirements: Java JDK 1.8 or above (authors used the version 1.8.0_181). Latest version can be found here [5]. After

successful installation of the JDK Maven can be installed (authors used version 3.6.0) following [1]. Latest version can be found here [5].

Installation: We cloned the repository or directly downloaded the ZIP file and unzipped it into a folder. In the folder we run the command: `mvn compile assembly:single`, which creates an executable JAR in the target folder.

Execution: We executed the the generated JAR with the following command in the previous used folder:

```
java -cp .\target\SIGIR2018-0.1-jar-with-dependencies.jar es.uam.ir.sigir2018.Main
```

After finished execution a results.txt file is available inside the used folder. We copied the results of this file into the figures.xlsx file, which is also provided by the authors of the paper in the unzipped folder. After we did this, similar graphs to the ones in the paper were displayed.

1.1 Datasets

MovieLens 1M Dataset: "These files contain 1,000,209 anonymous ratings of approximately 3,900 movies made by 6,040 MovieLens users who joined MovieLens in 2000." [4] We know a similar dataset already from our first Experiment Design for Data Science exercise. This dataset consist of 3 files users.txt, items.txt and data.txt.

User.txt: Contains the UserIDs.

Items.txt: Contains the MovieIDs.

Data.txt: Contains the ratings in the following format (tab separated, "::"). "UserID::MovieID::Rating::Timestamp

- UserIDs range between 1 and 6040

- MovieIDs range between 1 and 3952

- Ratings are made on a 5-star scale (whole-star ratings only)

- Timestamp is represented in seconds since the epoch as returned by time(2) - Each user has at least 20 ratings" [4]

Crowdsourced MAR Dataset: "These files contain 103,584 anonymous ratings on 1,084 music tracks entered by 1,054 CrowdFlower users between June 2015 and February 2016." [3] This dataset consist of also 3 files with exactly the same names users.txt, items.txt and data.txt.

User.txt: Contains the UserIDs.

Items.txt: Contains the MovieIDs.

Data.txt: Contains the ratings in the following format (tab separated, "::"). "UserID::TrackID::Rating::Known

- UserIDs range between 0 and 1054

- TrackIDs correspond to the track ids in Deezer

- Ratings range from 1 to 4, representing the five options users were given:

4 - "I really like it"

3 - "It's nice, I enjoy listening to it"

2 - "So-so"

1 - "I don't like it" or "Flawed audio, or not really music"

- Known indicates whether the user had already heard the track before (Known = 1) or not (Known = 0). - Each user has between 90 and 100 ratings." [4]

2 REPRODUCTION RESULTS

The exact metric values and figures could not be reproduced because there was no seed for the experiments. However, our results only change slightly compared to the paper results. This is because they used a method to run each experiment 10 times and average the results at the end, in order to reduce variance. This could also be the reason why they did not set a seed in the first place! To be sure, we will do some experiments regarding this and observe if our results differ a lot from those obtained in the paper.

To be able to get the same results in each execution, we modified the code to use an initial seed of our choice, since we could not find the seed that was used to obtain the paper results. Regarding the initial parameters used for the experiment, the number of repetitions is set to 10 and the number of folds for cross-validation is set to 5.

All the numerical results explained in the following subsections can be found in **results.txt* files in the GitHub repository¹. The figures of the experiments can be reproduced by pasting the numerical results in *figures.xlsx* excel sheet.

2.1 Reproduction of Figure 3

Figure 3 is affected by seed and split ratio. To reproduce this figure, since no seed was set, we initially set a seed of value 123 and run the experiment with the predefined split ratio of 0.8. Comparing our results with the paper results we observed some small differences in the metric values and figures, which can hardly be seen. In Figure 1 are displayed the graphical results of the discussed experiment while in the Table 1 and Table 2 we can see the actual deviation. The tables show only the results for a seed of value 123 and split ratio 0.8. Using a different seed (24) and split ratio 0.7, differences in the metric values were more noticeable. The metric values were higher, because the expected observed precision is using the formula: $(1 - \text{splitRatio}) * \text{precision}$ in the code. Graphically this resulted in higher bar charts, because the values on the y-axis are higher.

Figure 1: Graphical comparison of Figure 3. Right side are their results from [3], left side are our results using seed 123.

¹https://github.com/blendmexhuani/SIGIR2018_Reproduced

Table 1: Results comparison for Observed P@1

Recommendation	Our results	Their results	Abs deviation
Random	0.031224	0.031165	0.000060
Popularity	0.558273	0.557846	0.000427
Average rating	0.110468	0.110134	0.000334
Optimal	0.563114	0.562739	0.000375

Table 2: Results comparison for True P@1

Recommendation	Our results	Their results	Abs deviation
Random	0.500613	0.501633	0.001020
Popularity	0.710055	0.710721	0.000667
Average rating	0.859595	0.858475	0.001121
Optimal	0.999729	0.999725	0.000004

2.2 Reproduction of Figure 5

Apart from the initial seed, since they had repetitions for the experiments, we set another seed for each repetition, derived from the initial seed, by adding the repetition index to the latter. Experiments were performed with different seeds, while having 10 repetitions and 5 folds for cross-validation. Furthermore, we experimented with 5 folds and 10 folds for cross-validation while keeping the other parameters constant and additionally did some experiments with different values for repetitions (5, 10 and 20) using 5-fold cross-validation and seed value of 123.

2.2.1 Reproduction of Figure 5 a) All ratings.

To reproduce this figure, since no seed was set, we initially set a seed of value 123 and run the experiment while keeping the other parameters constant. Comparing our results with the paper results we observed some small differences in the metric values and figures, which can hardly be seen. In Figure 2 are displayed the graphical results of the discussed experiment while in the Table 3 and Table 4 we can see the actual deviation. Using a different seed (24), slightly different results were again obtained.

Furthermore, experimenting with different repetitions gave very similar results, but not identical. In contrast, when comparing experiments with 5 fold and 10 fold cross validation, we observed that the differences in the precision and nDCG are more visible this time. We have bigger deviation compared to other experiments. Observed precision and nDCG using 10-fold CV had smaller values.

2.2.2 Reproduction of Figure 5 b) Actual discovery (Mixed discovery dependencies).

In this scenario, observed precision is computed by counting only the items known to the user, while the true precision is calculated by using the full available MAR relevance information.

Since there was no initial seed and different results were obtained in each execution, we first set a seed of value 123 and run the experiment without changing the other parameters. We compared our results with paper results and there were slight differences in the metric values and figures. Using a different seed (24) slightly different results were again obtained. Results with minor differences were acquired when experimenting with different repetitions

Table 3: Results comparison for MovieLens 1M and Crowdsourced 100k Observed P@1

Recommendation	MovieLens 1M			Crowdsourced 100k		
	Our results	Their results	Abs deviation	Our results	Their results	Abs deviation
Random	0.006457	0.005596	0.000861	0.005787	0.005598	0.000190
Popularity	0.212517	0.209868	0.002649	0.015655	0.016053	0.000398
Average rating	0.140265	0.145894	0.005629	0.015446	0.015560	0.000114
Optimal	0.211325	0.210795	0.000530	0.021176	0.020323	0.000854

Table 4: Results comparison for MovieLens 1M and Crowdsourced 100k Observed nDCG@10

Recommendation	MovieLens 1M			Crowdsourced 100k		
	Our results	Their results	Abs deviation	Our results	Their results	Abs deviation
Random	0.003967	0.003846	0.000121	0.006667	0.006625	0.000041
Popularity	0.149997	0.149344	0.000653	0.022855	0.023149	0.000294
Average rating	0.101304	0.101965	0.000662	0.023606	0.023794	0.000188
Optimal	0.149323	0.149031	0.000292	0.028235	0.027963	0.000272

Figure 2: Graphical comparison of our reproduced Figure 5 a) (left side) and their Figure 5 a) (right side) from [3].

Figure 3: Graphical comparison of Figure 5 b) a) their results from [3] b) our results using seed 123, 10 repetitions, 5 folds c) our results using seed 123, 20 repetitions, 5 folds d) our results using seed 123, 10 repetitions, 10 folds.

as well. This was not the case when experimenting with different folds for cross-validation (5 and 10 folds). Keeping the other parameters constant, 5-fold and 10-fold cross-validation yielded visible differences for observed and true precision and nDCG in the figures and metric values when compared to one another. Graphical results of the discussed experiments (Crowdsourced data) are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 4: Graphical comparison of Figure 5 c) a) their results from [3] b) our results using seed 123, 10 repetitions, 5 folds c) our results using seed 123, 20 repetitions, 5 folds d) our results using seed 123, 10 repetitions, 10 folds.

2.2.3 Reproduction of Figure 5 c) Relevance-independent discovery. To reproduce this figure, since no seed was set, we initially set a seed of value 123 and run the experiment while keeping the other parameters constant. Comparing our results with the paper results we observed some small differences in the metric values and figures. Using a different seed (24), slightly different results were again obtained. Furthermore, experimenting with different repetitions gave very similar results, but not identical. In contrast, when comparing experiments with 5 fold and 10 fold cross validation, some differences in the observed precision and observed nDCG can be noticed, but the true precision remains similar. In Figure 4 are displayed the graphical results of the discussed experiments for Crowdsourced data.

2.2.4 Reproduction of Figure 5 d) Item-independent discovery. Similarly to above, the seed 123 was set and the experiment was run without changing the other parameters. There were some small noticeable differences in observed precision when comparing the results of this experiment with the paper result. Using a different seed (24), we attained very similar result compared to the latter experiment. In addition, slightly different results were obtained when experimenting with different repetitions. Trying different

Figure 5: Graphical comparison of Figure 5 d) a) their results from [3] b) our results using seed 123, 10 repetitions, 5 folds c) our results using seed 123, 20 repetitions, 5 folds d) our results using seed 123, 10 repetitions, 10 folds.

folds for cross-validation, however, there were different results regarding observed precision and nDCG when comparing results of 5-fold and 10-fold experiments with one another. The graphical results for the discussed experiment for Crowdsourced data are displayed in Figure 5.

2.3 Reproduction of Figure 6

In this figure, two variants of the user-based k nearest neighbors (kNN) algorithm are used:

- Normalized - known to be popularity-biased
- Not normalized - is biased towards the average rating

The popularity-biased algorithm appears to be clearly better than the one biased towards the average rating in terms of observed metric values, while the true values reveal rather the opposite.

Regarding the results, again, the exact metric values and figures could not be reproduced because there was no seed for the experiments. To be able to obtain the same results in each execution, since they had repetitions for the experiments, for each repetition we set another seed, derived from the initial seed we set at the beginning, by adding the repetition index to the latter. Experiments were performed with different seeds, while having 10 repetitions and 5-folds cross-validation. We experimented with 5 and 10 folds for cross-validation while keeping the other parameters constant. We also did some experiments with 5, 10 and 20 repetitions using 5-fold CV and seed value of 123.

2.3.1 Comparison and interpretation.

Since no seed was initially set by the authors of the paper, our results will differ every time we run the experiments, which is also stated in paper with the following: "Exact metric values change slightly from one execution to another" [2]. In order to compare our results with theirs, we set an initial seed at the beginning and also for each repetition a new seed, derived from the initial one.

In the Table 5 we have the deviations between our results, where we set the seed to 123, and the paper results. We can see that in all the cases we have very small differences which hardly observed in the figures generated. Those differences we try to observe by looking at the figure 6 where to the left side (a) are paper results and to right side (b) are our results.

Since we ran a couple more experiments by changing other parameters in the source code, above are explained each experiment run and our observation regarding those.

Figure 6: Graphical comparison of Figure 6 a) their results from [3] b) our results using seed 123, 10 repetitions, 5 folds

Experiment 1: since initially, no seed has been set, above we explained the differences of our results compared to those in the paper, by setting an initial seed. We now want to experiment using different seeds. By setting the seed to 24, we will check if the results will differ from those we got using seed 123. The other parameters are left untouched (10 repetitions, 5-fold CV). After running the experiment, we observed that the deviation is almost the same as the one above - our results differ from those from the paper with a slight difference which can be very hard to spot using figures.

Experiment 2: here we experimented using different number of fold in cross-validation technique and keeping the other parameters constant (10 repetitions, seed 123). After running this experiment using 5-fold and 10-fold CV, we observed that the differences are more visible this time. We have bigger deviation for Observed than True values but, there are no changes regarding which algorithm performed better.

Experiment 3: we also experimented using different number of repetitions while keeping the other parameters constant (5-fold CV, seed 123). After the experiment using 5, 10 and 20 repetitions, we observed that the deviation is almost the same as the one above - our results differ from those from the paper with a slight difference which can be very hard to spot using figures.

3 SUMMARY AND FINDINGS

In general, we were able to reproduce the results from the original paper but not the exact ones. However, they differ slightly from the original results. These differences were obtained because the authors initially did not use a seed for random generated numbers. We found it more convenient to modify the original code and set the seed where it was necessary, including the repetitions. Setting the seed number enabled us to make our experiments reproducible for each run. Taking into account that the authors averaged the results of experiments over 10 repetitions, our results did not differ much from the original results.

We ran experiments by changing different variables like: seed, split ratio, repetitions and folds of cross-validation depending on the figure. When experimenting with one variable, we kept the other variables constant in order to spot which of the variables has

Table 5: Results comparison for MovieLens 1M and Crowdsourced 100k

			User-based kNN	
			Non-normalized	Normalized
MovieLens 1M	Observed	Abs deviation P@1	0.002748	0.003444
		Abs deviation nDCG@10	0.000269	0.000817
Crowdsourced 100k	Observed	Abs deviation P@1	0.000054	0.000627
		Abs deviation nDCG@10	0.000478	0.000786
	True	Abs deviation P@1	0.000345	0.00103
		Abs deviation nDCG@10	0.000388	0.000036

the highest impact to the results. Overall, experimental results of different seeds and repetitions did not change much from one another, and original results. In contrast, experimenting with different split ratios and different cross-validation folds, yielded noticeable differences from the original paper.

Due to the provided GitHub repository and the documentation of the authors, the setup was straightforward. However, the paper was not very detailed on the parameters they set for the algorithms. This limited us on some additional experiments we could have performed but were unable to, since that would require a lot of time and detailed analysis of the code.

All of our experiments confirm the conclusions which were made in the paper. Regarding the figures, reproducing or creating new figures from our experiments' results was not difficult since the authors provided an excel sheet where we could paste our numerical results and the figures would be created automatically using those results.

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